

National Security and Emergency Preparedness Communications: Next Generation Priority Services

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Abstract— To ensure that National Security and Emergency Preparedness (NS/EP)-associated personnel can communicate during times of crisis, priority telecommunications services have been implemented over the past two decades within the public telephone networks of the United States. Emerging capabilities enabled by recent advances in communications protocols, network infrastructure, user device functionality and communication services are dramatically altering the working environment of society as a whole, including those with NS/EP responsibilities. Features such as video and data communications, enterprise mobility, and cloud services are becoming critical elements in the NS/EP toolkit, and thus candidates for future prioritization. The U.S. Government has embarked on efforts to define priority video communications and priority data transport services in the emerging Next-Generation Networks and to examine the risks and benefits with prioritization of other services.

We first describe the existing priority services, both in the wireless and the wired landline public networks. This background provides the basis for the subsequent discussion of on-going efforts to define and implement prioritization capabilities for emerging services to benefit NS/EP personnel as well as the technical and economic challenges associated with these activities.

I. INTRODUCTION

Wireless communications are becoming indispensable in all facets of life and even more so in emergency situations and disaster areas, where mobility can be critical and much of the wired communications infrastructure might be overloaded, damaged or destroyed. This point was brought home in the aftermath of the terrorist attacks on New York City and Washington, DC on 11 September 2001, when the damaged circuit-

switched telephone networks were unable to carry the suddenly enormous load of telephone calls.

Wireless networks are also susceptible to disasters, causing both excessive use and physical damage and resulting in traffic overload. Traffic prioritization, however, can ensure that those who have critical National Security and Emergency Preparedness (NS/EP) responsibilities during disasters and other emergencies can communicate even at times of network stress. Accordingly, the Office of Emergency Communications (OEC) [1] and former elements of the National Communications System [2]), an arm of the U.S. Federal Government, established a Wireless Priority Service (WPS) in 2002. WPS-authorized NS/EP callers may be accorded priority over public callers in gaining access to the cellular network resources and placing voice calls.

In addition to the WPS program, the OEC manages a wireline service, the Government Emergency Telecommunications Service (GETS). The OEC contracts with commercial telephony carriers to provide these priority services on their public networks to OEC-authorized individuals. The OEC authorizes potential WPS and GETS users, including officials of the Federal, State, local and tribal governments. Potential WPS and GETS users also include community leaders and first

responders, such as fire-fighters, medical personnel and law-enforcement officials. The subscriber record of each authorized WPS user is provisioned by the wireless carrier with the user's priority level and calling privileges, based on approval by the OEC. For GETS, the OEC issues each user a unique personal identification number (PIN) and calling privileges. Users can invoke the priority service on a per-call basis either from their own wireless handset by prefixing the dialed number with a special feature code, or from any other telephone (or wireless handset) by dialing a specific access number and entering the PIN in a manner similar to placing a calling-card call.

In anticipation of the migration of the public switched telephone networks (PSTN) from circuit-switching to Internet-Protocol (IP)-based, packet-switched infrastructures, the OEC initiated a set of activities to define and deploy priority capabilities for voice communications in the packet-network environment similar to priority capabilities available in the circuit-switched networks. These activities address the fact that communications in the packet-switched environment are not limited to voice but include multiple media (messaging, browsing, video, text and images, etc.). Users of emerging broadband wireless technologies are making extensive use of these new communications capabilities. To ensure that the benefits of these communication capabilities can be realized by NS/EP personnel during times of crisis, it is critical to examine, define and implement priority versions of these new IP-based services. The ongoing work in this area is the topic of this paper.

II. BACKGROUND

Communications services and the underlying network infrastructure have evolved significantly over the last 30 years, with the explosive growth of cellular telephony and the Internet as prime examples. As people have found new and innovative ways to communicate, they have become increasingly reliant upon these technologies. This reliance, and the economic benefits of the converged IP-based network, motivate the development of IP-based priority services. Priority services are meant to ensure that NS/EP personnel

have access to the services that they rely on during times of heavy demand and/or network degradation.

While priority could be implemented in many ways, the priority services defined and managed by the OEC in the United States have several common characteristics in their design and operation: First, these priority services provide priority *access* for authorized individuals. As an example, users of the priority telephony service have a higher probability of setting up a voice call connection. The second aspect of priority access is that the services managed by the OEC provide a benefit in gaining access to available resources, but do not involve preemption of resources currently in use by others. Third, the services are designed in a manner that ensures that NS/EP users do not consume excessive public resources to the detriment of the general public. In WPS, for example, priority calls are limited to a portion of the capacity of any cell site; priority call attempts made when that portion is occupied with existing priority calls are rejected or queued for available capacity. Finally, priority is granted only to authorized users. Individual users must obtain proper credentials from the OEC prior to using the services, and must actively invoke the priority service when needed; there is no "hotline" phone that always receives priority.

These priority services have evolved over time to meet the changing needs of those with NS/EP responsibilities. The GETS program became operational in 1995, providing priority access to wireline telephone service, the primary means of communication at the time [2]. The OEC began the implementation of a wireless priority service in 2002, just about the time the number of cellular telephones in the U.S. equaled the number of active land lines. Both GETS and WPS are designed to provide priority access to voice communications over the circuit-switched PSTN.

The commercial networks are rapidly evolving, with the legacy, circuit-switched networks potentially disappearing over the next ten years and the IP-based next-generation network (NGN) transforming the network infrastructures. The issues associated with this network change, the OEC NGN

program evolution, and the testing of priority voice services were discussed in [3].

The emerging services are the primary topic of this paper. A companion paper [8] provides some detail regarding the implementations of the OEC-specified service to date. As these services become more ingrained in the daily activities of NS/EP personnel, these users will come to expect to leverage these services in times of crisis.

In developing new priority services, it is important to recognize the limitations inherent in predicting the future. While it can be reasonably assumed that there will be future demand for priority video and data services, we are less certain how those services will be leveraged by NS/EP users. The OEC is investigating classes of services, and analyzing the priority needs of each class, with the aim of specifying the priority features that will operate regardless of the future user applications. The following sections describe these service classes and the issues associated with them.

III. ADVANCED NS/EP SERVICES

Implementation of priority services in the NGN poses significant challenges that differ from those encountered in the legacy telephone networks. Circuit-switched telephony has historically involved communications between two nearly identical user terminals (i.e., wire-line telephones) with well-defined capabilities. All calls used essentially the same communications capacity/bandwidth, and the telephony service provider controlled the end-to-end service environment. Once the connection (i.e., circuit) was established, quality of end-to-end communications was assured.

To offer a quality voice communication capability, NGN service providers will employ strict service performance control across all their networks, in an effort to replicate the circuit

switched experience. However, NGN is a multi-services infrastructure that supports not only voice telephony but also video communications and data services. This mix of services creates a challenge for NGN telephony in general, and for NS/EP priority services in particular, because these services will use varying amounts and multiple types of resources. As shown in Figure 1, these resources (marked by arrows) include both network capabilities, such as wireless channels and packet transport, as well as server resources, including request processing and communication ports. Serving the diverse and dynamic requirements of all these services concurrently complicates the challenge of delivering continuous connectivity, because the demand on network resources can fluctuate not only with the number of active services, but also with the specific mix of service types and even with the current activity of each service user. Additional complications arise from the fact that the resources required to offer these advanced services come from several domains, both commercial and technical. Priority services will only be able to provide a high likelihood of end-to-end success where priority treatments are present throughout the service path, including application servers, access networks, and across interconnecting networks. The increased number of service providers and increased complexity of services in the NGN represent a challenge to achieving the same level of ubiquitous support for

Figure 1: Resource access in advanced services

priority services as was provided by the legacy public telephony infrastructure.

The following sections describe the classes of advanced services that have been considered, looking at both the basic public service and the means for prioritization. These service classes include video telephony, information messaging and data access.

A. Video Telephony and Conferencing

Priority video services have been conceived as extensions of the corresponding commercial video services offered by service providers. Public video services are expected to enable subscribers to establish video sessions with destination parties. The request to establish such sessions may be similar to setting up a voice-telephony call or may involve Web- or message-based requests. Upon receiving a video session request, the network determines if the request can be honored with acceptable quality-of-service (QoS) for video and audio, or perhaps whether the audio bearer can be set up alone if insufficient resources exist for the video bearer. The request is then honored or rejected accordingly. If the network honors the request, the originating and destination parties' terminals initiate appropriate session negotiations and the session is established. The network then ensures the session is sustained with acceptable QoS.

Priority video sessions, as currently envisioned, might be invoked in a similar fashion, perhaps following several failed attempts (due to possible network congestion or damage) to invoke the non-priority service. If priority capacity is available, the call is established and the associated messages and corresponding media packets are marked so as to receive end-to-end priority. If no capacity is available, a priority session might be queued for a period of time, waiting for sufficient capacity to become available.

It should be noted that commercial, public video services are not yet available on service providers' next-generation networks. Furthermore, other NGN video services, different from those described here, may exist and may be given some priority treatment different from the video service described here.

However, the key aspects of priority access to network and server resources, and queuing for such resources, are common across all these instances.

B. Messaging

Messaging services include several forms of store-and-forward communications such as electronic mail (e-mail), instant messaging (IM), and short message service/multimedia message service (SMS/MMS). The priority messaging service will permit an OEC-authorized subscriber to send messages to a destination user (who may or may not be a priority-services subscriber), and to retrieve messages that have been received from other users (who may or may not be priority-services subscribers). The priority nature of the communications implies that messages will be expeditiously sent and received by the priority-services subscriber with high reliability even in situations when non-priority users may be experiencing severe service degradation.

Messaging services, in general, consist of three separate segments, and prioritization can be considered in each one of these segments:

- On the outbound leg, a connection-based data service permits a subscriber to initiate a priority data-transfer connection with a server for the purpose of sending outgoing messages;
- In the store-and-forward segment, an asynchronous data transfer process routes and transfers messages between the originator's messaging server and the intended recipient's server (possibly with several intermediate relay servers);
- On the inbound leg, either the message is actively delivered (pushed) to the recipient's device or a connection-based data service permits the recipient to retrieve the message from the server.

Ideally, a message sent with priority by an authorized priority user would receive end-to-end priority treatment. Providing priority to an authorized user during the transmission and retrieval of messages seems technically reasonable. Similarly, it is conceivable that the forwarding of priority messages between servers could be expedited. Providing priority in message retrieval for a recipient who is not an authorized user is problematic, given the need to authorize access to priority functionality, and the potential that a non-authorized user might have difficulty even

connecting to the server. Messaging services that push messages directly to the end-user device might be more amenable to ubiquitous priority messaging.

C. Data Access

The World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) [4] and other international standards organizations (e.g., [5],[6]) have specified sets of standards intended to facilitate convenient user access to information potentially distributed on a variety of different types of server platforms, such as Web sites and FTP servers. During times of congestion, service degradation may be experienced in the form of long response delays or failures to access designated servers, or in the form of error messages. A priority data service would provide authorized users with the means to interact with these remote data services in situations where corresponding public services experience severe degradation as a result of network congestion or server overload. Priority data access services will provide priority treatment to NS/EP users' Web browsing or file transfer in order to have near normal service performance in virtually all circumstances. Achieving such a result will require (a) priority treatment during access and connection to the network, (b) priority treatment during request/response processing by the data server(s) and (c) priority treatment in the transport of data packets between user device and server.

As envisioned, a priority-service user will invoke the data access service from within the data application (e.g., a Web browser). Once invoked, the user will be prompted to provide authorization credentials. The user will be expected to submit authorization credentials only once, independent of the number of query/response transactions exercised or different data servers accessed. A network-resident application triggered by the user's priority request will verify the user's authorization and then provide prioritization instructions to the appropriate servers, applications and network entities, facilitating priority treatment by priority-enhanced servers for all interactions, as well as bi-directional packet transport priority between the user's device and the servers. With the exception of the invocation and authorization stage, the user experience with these services should be the same as with the corresponding public service.

A key challenge with providing priority for this type of service-oriented access is the potential for congestion to occur not in the networks, which are managed by a few service providers, but in the servers themselves that are hosted by a vast number of entities around the world. As such, the end-to-end Data Access priority might be limited to a pre-defined set of servers. Priority network access to other sites would be provided by the Data Transport service.

D. Data Transport

Given the inability to determine which applications will be critical in the future, and to manage priority in all potential servers, it is desirable to offer a priority functionality that is independent of the application being used. Data transport priority differs from the other priority data services in that it provides priority treatment only for packet transport ("layer 3") but not for service processing. Priority treatment may be provided to data packets in the transport layer in several ways; for example, special handling at the network's routers, reserving a portion of each link's bandwidth for priority traffic, or establishing separate, reserved priority routes through the network. This priority transport treatment must be provided not only to the bearer packets which carry the voice, video, or data associated with the service, but also (and perhaps more importantly) to the packets that carry the signaling messages used to control each priority session.

Data transport may provide priority transport to all the packets associated with all data applications used by the NS/EP user, or it may be limited in scope (e.g., supports the transport of specific applications, or transport to/from specific destinations). The priority data transport service will still involve per-use invocation and user authorization.

To date, two priority data transport services have been identified featuring guaranteed and non-guaranteed bit-rates. Given the likely need for server enhancements to support other priority applications, one application of priority data may be to gain as much benefit as possible when dealing with non-enhanced application servers, such as

Web browsing across ordinary Web servers. In this case, priority transport can create a high probability of packets reaching the servers, but users may still experience poor performance as the servers' capacity may be nearing exhaustion. (In contrast, when an authorized user has invoked the full priority Data Access service, and the Web servers have been enhanced to support priority treatment of such services, priority treatment will be provided in Web server processing as well as in the transport of the Web service packets across the NGN.) Data transport is intended to function as an independent priority service that does not require enhanced application servers as other priority services do.

IV. DISCUSSION

There are multiple issues that must be addressed in order to implement these advanced services. Two that will be discussed here deal with the implementation of application-specific priority and the ability to gain initial access to the priority services.

There are several consequences associated with the implementation of application-level priority. In the first place, each application is invoked using its own protocol, and many of these protocols would need to be enhanced to be able to indicate the need for priority. For SIP-based voice and video signaling, this capability has been defined to include the Resource Priority Header [7]. The protocols for data access (i.e., HTTP, FTP) and messaging (POP/IMAP, SMTP) would likely need similar enhancements. Furthermore, even if the standards were extended to support data access priority, the ubiquitous deployment of these services would complicate roll-out of new versions supporting priority. Finally, in addition to the protocol enhancements, software clients would need to be enhanced to provide access to priority features, and server software would need to be enhanced to implement these features. Requiring customized capabilities on NS/EP users' devices would limit the range of terminals from which priority could be invoked, or require significant expenditures to incorporate this functionality into all client devices. The majority of organizations that operate data servers will have little or no need for the priority, and there is unlikely to be any mandate

for these organizations to deploy such capabilities. The current approach to deal with these issues is two-fold:

- 1) Initially focus on the definition and deployment of the Data Transport Priority service, which does not require new standards or server implementation.

- 2) In parallel with activities in standards development organizations, initiate consideration of enhancements to selected data access and messaging protocols to support OEC priority services, with the idea of focusing deployment on key servers of interest (e.g., those of U.S. Federal and State Government agencies).

A second significant issue associated with advanced priority services is ensuring that authorized users can gain access to them in the first place. In the implementation of the GETS wireline service, it was assumed that a user who had a phone with dial-tone could communicate with the local-exchange switch, regardless of load on that switch. Once the user dialed the GETS access number, the switch could provide provisional priority in order to collect the PIN that would confirm the user's authorization to employ the priority service. The situation is slightly different for WPS, where a user needs to have access to a wireless signaling channel to initiate a call: Such access may not be readily available during congestion. Base stations can, however, prohibit groups of handsets from initiating calls during overload conditions. The WPS service is implemented in a manner that exempts priority users from such prohibitions, thus increasing the likelihood of successful priority calls. In next-generation networks, which are similar to the WPS case, a shared medium connects the client devices to the network entities. In the case of next-generation wireless access, where the shared resource is managed by a network entity, an approach similar to that used in WPS seems appropriate. Wireline IP access technologies are less likely to have such a management entity; therefore, ensuring that users can invoke priority services in these cases is still an open issue.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper described a set of priority services that provide the means to ensure that NS/EP personnel can communicate during times of crisis. These services have been used in the past in wireline and

wireless networks and it is clear that technological advancement, in terms of network infrastructure, terminal capabilities and communication services, is providing new means of communication that NS/EP personnel will need to exploit in the future. The delivery of priority services in these emerging environments is an on-going effort, with technical, political and economic challenges.

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